

I want to engage in creative thinking for initiating
Digital Transformation in my organization

References:

- * Carvalho, J. Á. & J. Varajão, Digital Transformation Canvas[®], V1 (2016) – v10 (2021), Department of Information Systems, University of Minho.
- * Carvalho, J. Á. & J. Varajão (2021). Digital Transformation Canvas[®] (Version 10), Zenodo, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6656972

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Digital Transformation Canvas[®]

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Digital Transformation Canvas[®]

What is it?

The **Digital Transformation Canvas[®]** is a one-page overview that enables engaging in creative thinking for digital transformation initiatives. It is a valuable tool to create the basis for initiating and structuring the discussion about business improvement through information technologies.

Why should I use it?

XXI century's organizations cannot be competitive without information systems (IS) and information technologies (IT) leveraging their businesses. Due to the overwhelming diversity of IT and potential applications, can be a complex and risky endeavor to move forward to digital transformation in an ad-hoc way. The **Digital Transformation Canvas[®]** helps thinking about digital transformation in a creative and semi-structured approach.

? How can I use it?

There are several alternative ways of using the **Digital Transformation Canvas[®]**. The process can be started by: (A) Selecting one or more technologies to explore how they can be used to improve business; (B) Considering one or more trends to ascertain if they are interesting to be followed by the organization; (C) Selecting one or more business drivers to think about the transformations and technologies that are needed to address them (e.g., to enable a business strategy or improve the stakeholders' experience); (D) Defining the expected outcomes aiming at identifying the needed transformations and technologies. From this exercise should emerge new digital transformation projects (E) to be discussed and evaluated in the organization.

Technologies & IT-Enabled Practices	
<div style="border: 1px dashed gray; padding: 2px; display: inline-block;"> Stable Emerging Frontier Exponential </div>	
Sensors RFID Transponders GPS Satellites Mobile computing Wearable computers Wearable devices Biometric devices	Mobile devices Energy/Batteries Flash memory Ubiquitous computing IoT - Internet of Things 3D printing Other:
Robotics Self-driving cars Drones Quantic Computing SOC - Service Orientation Computing	Artificial Intelligence Machine Learning Cognitive Agents Chatbots Other:
Interfaces Natural interfaces Voice recognition Behavior recognition Pattern recognition Digital signature	Augmented reality Virtual reality Computer vision Other:
Big Data Business Intelligence Analytics Data mining Text mining Process mining Sentiment Analysis Information Harvesting Information visualization	Personal Information Personal Data Store Open Data Search practices (Googling) Other:
Meta-information Semantic Web Linked Data	

Trends
Personalization BYOD - Bring Your Own Device Participation Self-Service Once Only Proactive Service Delivery Gamification Inclusion Data monetization
Multi-channel Digital by default Subscription Economy Sharing Economy Service Productization Product Servicization Green X (e.g., Green Computing) Crowd-X (e.g., Crowd-sourcing) Work Nature Other:

Business Drivers
Inner change > Processes > People > Infra-structure Outer change > Market > Legislation Problems Opportunities Other:
Business
<div style="border: 1px solid gray; padding: 5px; display: inline-block;">Strategy</div>
<div style="border: 1px solid gray; padding: 5px; display: inline-block;">Success Factors</div>
<div style="border: 1px solid gray; padding: 5px; display: inline-block;">Stakeholders</div>
Customers Suppliers Business partners Employees Shareholders Other:

Business Impacts
Department(s) Group(s) Process(es) Job(s) Workplace(s) Other:
Organization Branch(s) Division(s)

Expected Outcomes
Income Cost Accessibility Security Privacy Rastreability Auditability Governance Accountability Sustainability Social responsibility Agility Intelligence Resilience Other:
Market Competitive capability Stakeholder experience Business model Product/Service Management practice Operational process Efficiency Operational capability Reputation Information Immediacy/real-time

Cloud Web (e.g., portals) Apps Social Networks ePayments Blockchain Bitcoin Social Business Simulation Tele-X (e.g. Tele-assistance)	XaaS (X as a Service) e-Business e-Commerce B2X (e.g. B2C, B2B, B2A) Geo-reference Chrono-reference Document Management Content Management Workflow Management Other:	ERP - Enterprise Resource Management CRM - Customer Relationship Management SCM - Supply Chain Management BPM - Business Process Management CEM/UEM - Customer/User Experience Management KM - Knowledge Management IM - Innovation Management OAM - Organisational Attention Management GIS - Geographic Information Systems Other:
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